

COMPARISON OF ORAL PROGESTERONE WITH PER RECTAL PESSARY IN DECLINING THE INCIDENCE OF PRETERM LABOUR AT <34 WEEKS OF GESTATION IN SINGLETON PREGNANCIES

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Abstract

Introduction: Oral, intramuscular, subcutaneous, vaginal gel, vaginal capsules, and micronized progesterone pessary are all forms of progesterone. Although there is some evidence that micronized progesterone pessary is superior to other presentations in preventing PTB, the pessary appears to work by mechanically altering the cervico-uterine angle, minimizing cervix compression and protecting cervical mucus.

Objective: To evaluate the efficacy of oral progesterone with per rectal pessary in declining the incidence of preterm labour at <34 weeks of gestation in singleton pregnancies.

Materials and Procedures: 160 women between the ages of 18 and 40 who were between the gestational ages of 24 and 36 weeks and at risk of premature labor were included. Patients with uterine malformations, malformed fetuses, and multiple gestations were not included. A computer-generated random number table was used to divide the patients into two equal groups at random. Patients in Group B received 400 mg of cyclogest pessary per rectal use at bedtime, while Group A received 10 mg of oral progesterone twice day. The patients were monitored till 37 weeks of pregnancy. Efficacy was evaluated.

Results: Participants in the study were between the ages of 18 and 40, with an average age of 29.44 ± 3.92 years. The ladies in groups A and B were, respectively, 29.86 ± 4.54 and 29.34 ± 3.46 years old. Of the 90 patients, most (56.25%) were between the ages of 31 and 40. A p-value of 0.0129 indicated that 56 (70.0%) in group A (oral progesterone) and 69 (86.25%) in group B (cyclogest pessary) were effective in avoiding premature delivery.

Conclusion: This study concluded that efficacy of cyclogest pessary is better than oral progesterone for treating preterm labour.

INTRODUCTION

Preterm delivery is becoming a significant issue on a global scale. due to its increasing prevalence in recent decades.¹ Worldwide,

preterm birth rates range from 5% to 18%.^{2,3} Preterm birth (PTB) is the second highest cause of death for children under five years old and

the most common cause of newborn morbidity and mortality globally.^{4,5} Survivors may be at risk for lifelong visual and hearing loss, cerebral palsy, intellectual disability, and chronic lung illness, among other serious disabilities.⁶ Additionally, they have a higher chance of acquiring diabetes, hypertension, and developmental issues in later life. In order to improve the health of mothers and children, PTB prevention has thus been regarded as a global priority.⁷

Preterm labor's pathophysiology is poorly understood, and it's frequently unclear if it's the consequence of a pathologic mechanism or early idiopathic activation of the regular labor process. There are several ideas about how labor begins, such as 1) oxytocin initiation, 2) progesterone withdrawal, and 3) early decidual activation.³ The onset of preterm labor is most likely caused by premature decidual activation. Although the fetal-decidual paracrine system and possibly intrauterine hemorrhage may play a role, decidual activation often occurs in the context of an undetected upper genital tract infection, particularly in cases involving early preterm labor.^{3,4}

The identification of risk factors in obstetrical history, biochemical markers, and short cervix provides the foundation for PTB prevention in singleton pregnancies. Asymptomatic short cervix in the second trimester and a history of PTB are both reliable indicators of PTB.⁸ By reducing the production of stimulatory prostaglandins and suppressing the expression of genes associated with contraction-related proteins, progesterone is a key factor in preserving uterine quiescence throughout the latter half of pregnancy, according to recent studies. Moreover, both term and preterm labor are associated with the functional cessation of progesterone action (at the uterine level).³ Oral, intramuscular, subcutaneous, vaginal gel, vaginal capsules, and micronized progesterone pessary are all forms of progesterone. Although there is some evidence that micronized progesterone pessary is superior to other presentations in preventing PTB, the pessary appears to work by mechanically altering the cervico-uterine angle,

minimizing cervix compression, and protecting cervical mucus.⁹

These days, preterm delivery is a prevalent issue, and obstetric care has a significant obstacle in preventing it. There aren't many research comparing the use of cyclogest pessary with oral progesterone to prevent premature delivery. In order to reduce the associated neonatal morbidity and death, the findings of this study will be useful in choosing the most effective preventative approach to dissuade preterm birth in individuals at risk of preterm labor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

With ethical review committee approval, 160 patients (80 in each group) aged 18 to 40 with gestational ages <34 weeks and preterm labor risk (previous history of preterm birth, short cervical length (< 2.5 cm) on anomaly scan) took part in this comparative, cross-sectional study from June 1, 2024, to November 30, 2024. With a 5% level of significance, 80% research power, $P1 = 69.7\%$ ³, and $P2 = 88.8\%$ ³, the sample size was calculated to be 160, or 80 cases in each group, using the WHO calculator for two proportions. Patients with multiple gestations, uterine malformations, and malformed fetuses were excluded.

A computer-generated random number table was used to divide the patients into two equal groups at random. Patients in Group B received 400 mg of cyclogest pessary per rectal use at bedtime, while Group A received 10 mg of oral progesterone twice day. The patients were monitored till 37 weeks of pregnancy. Effectiveness (avoidance of premature birth). A baby born before 37 weeks of pregnancy was considered a preterm birth. In order to follow up, the patient's phone number was obtained. The researcher herself gathered all the data on a freshly created proforma (attached).

SPSS version 25 was used to enter and evaluate the data. The evaluation of descriptive data included the mean and standard deviation of numerical variables such as age, parity, number of prior preterm deliveries, gestational age at baseline, gestational age at delivery, and BMI. For qualitative variables like efficacy, frequency and percentage were computed, and the chi-square test was used to compare the two groups.

RESULTS:

The study's participants ranged in age from 18 to 40, with a mean age of 29.44 ± 3.92 years. The average age of the women in groups A and B was 29.86 ± 4.54 and 29.34 ± 3.46 years, respectively. According to Table I, the majority of the 90 patients (56.25%) were between the ages of 31 and 40. The mean gestational age is 28.12 ± 3.34 weeks, (gestational age ranged from less than 34 weeks). Group B's mean gestational age was 28.09 ± 3.42 weeks, while group A's was 27.20 ± 3.30 weeks. Group A and Group B had mean gestational ages at delivery of 36.87 ± 2.11

weeks and 37.45 ± 1.42 weeks, respectively. BMI was 28.91 ± 3.44 kg/m² on average. Table II displays the patient distribution by parity. Table III displays the distribution of patients by prior h/o preterm birth.

According to Table IV, 56 (70.0%) in group A (oral progesterone) and 69 (86.25%) in group B (cyclogest pessary) demonstrated efficacy (in terms of preventing preterm birth), with a p-value of 0.0129.

Table-I: Distribution of patients according to age.

Age (years)	Group A (n=80)		Group B (n=80)		Total (n=160)	
	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
18-30	32	40.0	38	47.50	70	43.75
31-40	48	60.0	42	52.50	90	56.25
Mean \pm SD	29.86 ± 4.54		29.34 ± 3.46		29.44 ± 3.92	

Table II: Distribution of patients according to parity.

Parity	Group A (n=80)		Group B (n=80)		Total (n=160)	
	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
Primiparous	17	21.25	15	18.75	32	20.0
Multiparous	63	78.75	65	81.25	128	80.0

Table-III: Distribution of patients according to h/o preterm birth

h/o preterm birth	Group A (n=80)		Group B (n=80)		Total (n=160)	
	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
Yes	38	47.50	39	48.75	77	48.13
No	42	52.50	41	51.25	83	51.87

Table IV: Comparison of Efficacy between both Groups (n=160).

		Group A (n=80)		Group B (n=80)	
		Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
EFFICACY	Yes	56	70.0	69	86.25
	No	24	30.0	11	13.75

➤ P value is 0.0129 which is statistically significant.

DISCUSSION:

Nowadays, progestin-based medications come in a variety of forms. Progesterone treatment may

generally lower the incidence of preterm deliveries in women with short cervixes or a history of preterm labor, based on the findings

of earlier research.^{10,11} To determine more specific details regarding the formulation, mode of administration, ideal dosage, possible hazards, and potential adverse effects of progesterone on perinatal outcomes, more research is necessary. Additionally, a comparison of the available progestin medications should be conducted in order to determine which are the safest and most effective.^{12,13} In this study, I compared the effects of oral progesterone and per rectal pessary in reducing the risk of preterm labor at less than 34 weeks gestation in singleton pregnancies.

Participants in the study were between the ages of 18 and 40, with an average age of 29.44 ± 3.92 years. The ladies in groups A and B were, respectively, 29.86 ± 4.54 and 29.34 ± 3.46 years old. Of the 90 patients, most (56.25%) were between the ages of 31 and 40. With a mean age of 28.12 ± 3.34 weeks, gestational age ranged from less than 34 weeks. Group B's mean gestational age was 28.09 ± 3.42 weeks, while group A's was 27.20 ± 3.30 weeks. Group A and Group B had mean gestational ages at delivery of 36.87 ± 2.11 weeks and 37.45 ± 1.42 weeks, respectively. BMI was 28.91 ± 3.44 kg/m² on average. These results were similar to those of the earlier research.^{14,15}

In my study, 56 (70.0%) in group A (oral progesterone) and 69 (86.25%) in group B (cyclogest pessary) showed efficacy (in terms of preventing preterm birth), with a p-value of 0.0129. According to a study, oral progesterone and cyclogest pessary were both effective in preventing preterm birth (69.7% and 88.8%, respectively), while preterm birth was observed in 30.7% of the oral progesterone group and 13.75% of the cyclogest pessary group.³

Patients were split into two groups for a local randomized controlled experiment¹⁶ that was carried out at the Combined Military Hospital Nowshera's Gynecology and Obstetrics department. Group B received 400 mg of cyclogest pessary per rectal use, while Group A received 10 mg of oral progesterone twice a day. With 1:1 randomization, 152 patients in total—76 in each group—were enrolled in the trial. 29.6 weeks \pm 1.5 SD was the mean gestational

age. Premature C-section, maternal systemic side effects, tocolysis use, NICU admissions, perinatal death, intraventricular hemorrhage, oxygen use at the 28th day of life, and retinopathy of prematurity are all reduced when micronized progesterone cyclogest pessary was used per rectal usage ($p < 0.05$). Neither of the two interventional groups showed a significant correlation with birth weight, prenatal corticosteroid use, respiratory distress syndrome, pneumonia, or sepsis ($p > 0.05$).¹⁶

Elder et al. claim that per-rectal progesterone lowers perinatal mortality ($p < 0.05$) by reducing uterine contraction and preterm birth.¹⁷ Another study found that when compared to oral progesterone, micronized progesterone cyclogest pessary was helpful in reducing perinatal death, intraventricular hemorrhage, maternal systemic utilization, tocolysis use, premature C-section, and NICU hospitalizations. Women who use vaginal progesterone are less likely to give birth preterm or need medical intervention, according to similar research.¹⁸ Progesterone is also associated with less maternal issues, according to similar research ($p = 0.00$).¹⁹

According to published research, vaginal pessaries are more successful than a placebo at preventing preterm birth. Progesterone use, however, is linked to a decrease in prenatal tocolysis.²⁰ According to a related study, using injectable and percutaneous progesterone is more beneficial than oral progesterone at preventing premature births ($p = 0.01$).²¹

Patients in the current study who received cyclogest pessary progesterone by rectal usage expressed more satisfaction than those who received a placebo ($p = 0.00$). According to Hack et al., patients expressed greater satisfaction with oral progesterone than with vaginal progesterone ($p = 0.01$).²² According to a related study, women expressed greater satisfaction with rectal progesterone use than vaginal ($p = 0.02$).²³

Two limitations of our study were a small patient population and a single-center design. Although a wide range of problem-related data has been collected, it may not fully reflect the rate of difficulties associated with the procedure.

Thus, larger population-based studies with long-term follow-up should be the main focus of future study.

CONCLUSION:

According to the study's findings, cyclogest pessary is more effective than oral progesterone

at treating premature labor. Therefore, we suggest that cyclogest pessary be used as a first-line treatment to prevent preterm labor. This will allow corticosteroid administration to speed up fetal lung maturation, which will help to lower perinatal mortality and morbidity for both the mother and the fetus.

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